

Social Network Rumor Diffusion Predication Based on Equal Responsibility Game Model

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ABSTRACT: A rumor's substance may now spread more quickly than ever before because to the interconnection between social networks and mobile sensor networks made possible by the billions of mobile phones in circulation. Consequently, rumour dissemination is a major concern in those two networks, and predicting rumour diffusion is of utmost importance when dealing with rumours that initially have a limited influence. Modern diffusion models, on the other hand, only account for the effects on large groups and not on individuals in the microcosm. So, in the early stages of rumour dissemination, when there is only one rumour spreader, they aren't a good fit for rumour dispersion prediction. We provide a new model based on game theory, the Equal Responsibility Rumour spread Game Model (ERRDGM), to describe the rumour spread process and address that issue. The model begins by showing the spread of a rumour as a game in which people compete with their neighbours to see who can retweet the most content in order to earn the most money. Then, once the game reaches a Nash equilibrium, we construct a graph to predict the spread of rumour based on how well each player has spread the word.

dispersion of rumours. This theory states that even when there are initially only a small number of rumour spreaders, our ERRDGM model can capture the influence of microcosmic persons on the diffusion process and allow us to carry it out. Based on both the diffusion size and the social network structure, our ERRDGM model is able to provide more accurate predictions for rumour spread, according to our simulation findings.

KEYWORDS: ERRDGM, Mobile phones, Social network, State-of-the-art diffusion.

I.INTRODUCTION: To hasten the dissemination of data in today's digital world, billions of multipurpose phones were used. Cell phones, as one kind of sensor in sensor organisation, do double duty: they establish a virtual informal community and provide data to a massive sensor network. An organisation of social entertainers (such as individuals or groups), sets of dyadic links, and other forms of social communication amongst actors constitute a social network, according to Wikipedia [1]. Rumours spread like wildfire via a web of personal connections made possible by the complex interpersonal organisation structure. According to Peterson and Gist [2], gossip is defined as a

imaginative account of events that pass from one person to another and are connected to a topic, event, or thing that is publicly known and debated. All gossipy tidbits were confirmed by experts as they were tagged by humans in our study. We nevertheless expect reliable authorities to correctly classify pieces of gossip and decipher the current state of rumour analysis, even though authorities do make mistakes and declare posts to be talk on occasion.

When it comes to the dissemination of gossip, the informal organisation and the sensor network work closely together; the former handles the transmission of gossip content, while the latter handles the semantic diffusion sway. Despite their differences in structure and work, they collaborate intently in this regard. One of the major issues with online media is the rapid dissemination of rumours via mobile phones, which is happening more quickly than ever before in sensor networks and social organisations. False information spread considerably more rapidly, deeply, and extensively than other true data on Twitter, according to Vosoughiet al. [3]. From 2006 to 2017, three million people participated in their project, which included the dissemination of around 126,000 tales. False news was more novel than real information, and people were obligated to spread fresh information, even if the researchers hadn't shown whether morsels of gossip are distributed faster than breaking news in the study. Gossip, according to Soroush Vosoughi's ruling, will pose a threat to the state-of-the-art in lazy speech analysis and significantly impact

enormous influence on actual society from online informal groups. Weibo, the most popular microblog in China, was responsible for 59% of all gossip in 2015, according to the Chinese Academy of Social Science's New Media Blue Book [4] (Figure 1). Because of its massive user base and ease of use, Weibo has become a popular platform for Chinese gossip.

There are two parts of the typical conversation that is beneficial to casing system that deal with gossipy bits: identifying the gossip and predicting how the rumour will spread. Since the impact of a rumour cannot be reliably predicted at the gossip identification stage, talk dissemination prediction is essential. We can learn about the data dispersion size and structure with the help of the talk diffusion prediction, which allows us to find pieces of gossip that will have a huge impact on the future. Although the tiny astronomical individual impact is important, top-tier dispersion models ignore it in favour of the more obvious gathering effect. Therefore, using them to test the gossip dispersion prediction in the early stages of rumour spreading with a single talk spreader is not a good idea.

The spread of shocking news is quite different from the spread of gossip. When customers sense gossip, their attention is drawn to whether or not it is really conversation. On the other side, when customers hear terrible news, they will focus on the point and how they feel about it. Accordingly, although the majority of customers won't disperse conversation, they will diffuse shocking news several times over a range of emotions and subjects. The attention dispersion cycle for customers is like a game.

cycle because many individuals would spread a few postings that will boost their authority in a social group. In this study, we want to demonstrate the rumour dissemination measure as a single game cycle and establish the structure of the diffusion network, dispersion grid, and dispersion scale. In order to rearrange the game model, we take the Equal Responsibility assumption in speech distribution as a given, which means that we ignore the dissemination substance and any changes to it. Instead, we model asocial individual behaviour based on income and risk.

EXISTING SYSTEM: A rumor's substance may now spread more quickly than ever before because to the interconnection between social networks and mobile sensor networks made possible by the billions of mobile phones in circulation. Consequently, rumour dissemination is a major concern in those two networks, and predicting rumour diffusion is of utmost importance when dealing with rumours that initially have a limited influence. Modern diffusion models, on the other hand, only account for the effects on large groups and not on individuals in the microcosm. So, in the early stages of rumour dissemination, when there is only one rumour spreader, they aren't a good fit for rumour dispersion prediction.

PROPOSED SYSTEM: We provide a new model based on game theory, the Equal Responsibility Rumour spread Game Model (ERRDGM), to describe the rumour spread process and address that issue. The model begins by showing the spread of

rumour diffusion prediction graph, which shows the scale and structure of rumour diffusion in a social network, is built when the process as a game between individuals and their neighbours who choose to re-tweet or not according to their revenues from the game of diffusion. Second, when the game reaches the Nash equilibrium state, the players will share the responsibility of spreading a rumour in calculating their revenues from the game. This theory states that even when there are initially only a small number of rumour spreaders, our ERRDGM model can capture the influence of microcosmic persons on the diffusion process and allow us to carry it out. Based on the findings of our experiments, it seems that our ERRDGM model is capable of producing more precise predictions of rumour dissemination based on both the diffusion size and the social network structure.

RESULTS:

Home screen

Server login

Server home page

Add products

View all users and authorize

Product add status

View all request and response details

View all products

Add category

Add category status

Products full details

Tweet details

Search friends

User registration

Search result

User registration

View request status

User home screen

View all friends

Recommend product to friends

All users of my country

User recommended products

Retweet friends

Rumor diffusion attack

View rumors

II.CONCLUSION

Due to the complex informal community structures and individual dissemination intents, talk dispersion prediction is a test effort. We provide an ERRDGM model that relies on the assumption that the spreaders would divide up the work of spreading gossip in order to replicate the early stage of gossip dispersion's measurement of talk dissemination. We use game theory to simulate the revenue from dissemination in this process. The findings of the experiments demonstrate that our model

successfully mimics the rumour transmission cycle in informal societies, with outcomes that are comparable to those of real dissemination organisations. However, individual characteristic is not included in our model. As a result, moving forward with our projects, we will include client feedback into user profiles, which will help us understand why people disperse speech on a personal level.

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